

Contrastive Analysis of Adverb Elements Functioning in Indonesian Language and Tontemboan Local Language

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ABSTRACT: The purpose of this study is to describe the contrast of adverb functioning elements in Indonesian Language and Tontemboan language. The adverb elements meant in this research is the types of adverb in Indonesian language that refers to the theoretical basis by Moeliono, A. et al in Tata Bahasa Baku Bahasa Indonesia (fourth edition) to wit adverb of place, adverb of time, adverb of tool, adverb of purpose, adverb of manner, adverb of accompaniment, comparative adverb, adverb of interchangeability, adverb of causative, adverb of consequence, adverbs of quantity, adverbs of quality, adverbs of viewpoint. There are also other types of adverbs in the form of subordinate clauses such as adverbs of requirement, conditional adverbs, consensual adverbs, and adverbs of result. Data collection techniques and tools were obtained through direct observation, interviews and literature study. The data analysis technique used the padan technique in determining the lingual units of adverbs. The lingual unit of the Tontemboan language is adjusted, harmonized, matched, and equated with the determining element identity, which is the Adverb elements Functioning in Indonesian language, as there are subject and predicate as the mandatory elements filled in the sentences. The results showed that the types of syntactic adverb functioning in Indonesian language and Tontemboan languages have similarities and differences. The similarities can be seen from the total number types of adverbs, there are thirteen types of adverbs in Indonesian exist in Tontemboan language. The difference is that some adverb elements sentences in Indonesian language that used the prepositions and conjunctions cannot be identified in the Tontemboan local language.

KEYWORDS- Adverb Types, Indonesian Language, Tontemboan Local Language

I. INTRODUCTION

Tontemboan language is a language spoken in some areas of Minahasa region and the South Minahasa region. This local language is one of the languages that is threatened with the danger of extinction if preventions are not being carried out. Generations aged 50 and under, tend to use Manado Malay in their interactions. Likewise, speakers of Tontemboan language are decreasing because Tontemboan language is no longer used as first language by the old people. They tend to communicate with Manado Melayu more often in their daily conversations.

The threat of Tontemboan language extinction has raised the awareness of the speakers to start doing the preventions. One of the ways to overcome this extinction is the need to inherit the languages using the strategy of contrasting two languages: a language that threatened to be extinct, and Indonesian language that is used to characterize the national identity.

Contrastive analysis is used to identify the structural differences and similarities between two languages or more. The differences in language structure will provide the insight on how certain people's mindsets are reflected in the language they use (Wijaya I Dewa Putu, 2021). Contrastive analysis is the method used to find out the differences between the first language (L1) and the target language (L2) which often confound the second

language learners in understanding their learning material (Brown, 1973). Contrastive linguistics compares two languages (or more). All of the components would be synchronized in order to find out the differences, and similarities from the languages compared (Moeliono: 1988:32).

Several studies related to the Tontemboan local language have been carried out, but the studies about contrastive analysis of adverbs functioning in Tontemboan Language and Indonesian language have not been obtained. The writer has found out some online researches, such as 1) Palar Revlin "Category of Aspects in Tontemboan Language" labbineka.kemdikbud.go.id 2) S1 student article "Suffixes in English and Tontemboan Language" media.neliti.com 3) Robot Kevin

"Absolute Directions in Tontemboan Language" Unsrat journal, 2019 4) Pongantung OS

"Tontemboan Language Suffix" Unima journal, 2020 and 5) Mundung "Tontemboan Language Verbs (A Contribution to Regional Language Learning in South Minahasa Regency)" Unima journal 2020.

Contrast analysis of adverbs functioning in Tontemboan Language and Indonesian language is interesting to be studied because there are so many adverbs elements found in Tontemboan language. Unlike Subject and Predicate that necessary appear in the sentences as requirements, adverbs in Tontemboan Language can appear only as an extension of the sentence. This is related to the statement of Moeliono, et al (2017) that said grammatically, a sentence consists of subject and predicate which can be followed by objects, complements, and/or adverbs. The use of objects, complements, and/or adverbs necessary depends on the predicate filling verb. A sentence contraction is not only affected by the sentence that precedes it, but also affects the sentence that comes after it. Thus, in a discourse (text) there are sentences that only consist of one phrase or one word. From its syntactic function, the phrase or word, can come as a subject, predicate, object, complement, or adverbs. This syntactic adverb functioning are what meant in this paper.

Therefore the purpose of this study is to describe the contrast of adverbs functioning elements in Indonesian language and Tontemboan language. The adverbs elements referred is the type of adverbs used in Indonesian language and the Tontemboan language. Types of Adverbs in Indonesian according to the theoretical basis of this study refers to Tata Bahasa Baku Bahasa Indonesia (fourth edition), they are adverb of place, adverb of time, adverb of tool, adverb of purpose, adverb of manner, adverb of accompaniment, comparative adverb, adverb of interchangeability, adverb of causative, adverb of consequence, adverbs of quantity, adverbs of quality, adverbs of viewpoint. There are also other types of adverbs in the form of subordinate clauses such as adverbs of requirement, conditional adverbs, consensual adverbs, and adverbs of result. These types of adverbs are explained in the results sections and still refer to the Indonesian Standard as explained above.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

This research uses a contrastive approach, the main source of this research data is in the form of Indonesian language sentences that include Adverb Functions. The examples of these sentences with Adverb Functions are contrasted with the sentences in Tontemboan language. This is intended to identify the differences and similarities between the two languages. Thus, the method used in this study is a qualitative descriptive method that seeks to describe the sentences that contained with adverb functioning from both languages just as they are.

Data collection techniques and tools were obtained through direct observation, interviews and literature study. The list of questions was compiled based on the Indonesian Standard Grammar (2017) and then adjusted to the conditions in the field. The questions lists are filled by the informants who use the Tontemboan language actively, especially in the scope of mastering sentence structures that have adverb functioning. The research location is the area of Tontemboan Local Language speakers, especially in Tareran District.

The data analysis technique used the *padan* technique in determining the lingual units of adverbs. The lingual unit of the Tontemboan language is adjusted, harmonized, matched, and equated with the determining

element identity, which is the Adverb elements Functioning in Indonesian language, as there are subject and predicate as the mandatory elements filled in the sentences.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Adverbs have the most diverse syntactic function. It is really convenient to be placed. Adverbs can appear at the end, beginning and middle of a sentence. In general, the presence of adverbs in sentences is arbitrary. Adverb constituents are usually in the form of prepositional phrases, nouns or nominal phrases, numerals or numeral phrases, or adverb phrases, (Moeliono, et al. 2017).

The following study describes each type of Adverbs, both in Indonesian and in the language of the Tontemboan Region.

3.1 ADVERBS OF PLACE

Adverb of place indicates the place where an event or situation occurs. Unlike adverb of time, adverb of place can only be filled with prepositional phrases. The prepositions used are *di*, *ke*, *dari*, *sampai*, and *pada*. After the preposition there are words describe the place characteristics such as *di sini*, *di sana*, *dari sana*, *dari sini*, *ke mana*, *dan dari situ*. In addition to the forms above, prepositions can also be joined with other nouns to form adverb of place as long as the noun has semantic characteristics that contain a place meaning. Words such as *jembatan*, *rumah*, *Jakarta*, and number that has semantic characteristics such as *tempat*, *tetapi pukul*, *tanggal*, *dan tahun*.

- 1) *Di sana* akan dilakukan peletakan batu pertama.
A mange bitu sera lumukut im batu ketare
The groundbreaking ceremony will be held there.
- 2) Buku itu diletakkan *di atas* meja.
Si buku tu awekar an dangke im meja
The book is placed on the table
- 3) Anatje berangkat *dari rumah* pukul enam.
Anatje mayak am bale jam 6
Anatje left the house at six o'clock.
- 4) Keluarganya akan pindah *ke Manado*.
Pamale era meru am Benang
Her family will move to Manado.
- 5) Saya akan menemanimu sampai *jembatan gantung*.
Yaku kumora pi ico akan ina dodoku gantung
I will accompany you to the hanging bridge.
- 6) Kasus itu sudah *sampai ke atas*.
Si perkara aniok makerem an dangkek
That case is brought to higher level.
- 7) Dokumen itu ada *di bawah* sekali.
Si dokumen tu an darem keli
The document is on the down.
- 8) Pemasangan antena itu dilakukan *dari dalam*.
Si antena tu ayuntep anuntup in dano
The antenna is placed from the inside.
- 9) Mereka memang berjalan *di belakang*.
sera mayak am समय
They walk from the back.
- 10) Paspur itu ada *di* meja.
Si paspor tu andangka i meja
The passport is at the table
- 11) Paspur itu ada *di atas* meja.
Si paspor tu aweyen andangka i meja

- The passport is on the table*
- 12) Uangnya disimpan di lemari.
Roit na ayuntep anumtep i lamori
The money is in the cupboard.
- 13) Uangnya disimpan di dalam lemari.
Roit na anumtep i lumora
The money is placed inside the cupboard.
- 14) Buku itu ada di lemari.
Si buku tu anumtep i lemari
The book is at the cupboard.
- 15) Buku itu ada di atas meja.
Si buku tu aweyan andengka i meja
The book is on the table.
- 16) Uangnya ada di meja.
Roit na aweyan a meja
The money is at the table.
- 17) Uangnya ada di bawah meja.
Roit na na tuandarem i meja
The money is inside the table
- 18) Ayah ada di rumah.
Si papa aweyan ambale
Father is at home
- 19) Ayah ada di dalam rumah.
Si papa na anuntem pimambale
Father is inside the house.

Based on the data from the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian language and the Tontemboan language have the same place descriptions, as explained in of Adverbs of Place.

3.2 ADVERBS OF TIME

Adverb of time provides information about when an event occurs. The adverb function is filled with various forms (a) single words, (b) nominal phrases, and (c) prepositional phrases. In general, adverbs of time are placed at the back of the sentence, but can also be placed in the middle or in front of the sentence. Adverbs of time in the form of several singular words are *pernah*, *sering*, *selalu*, *kadang-kadang*, *biasanya*, *kemarin*, *sekarang*, *besok*, *lusa*, *tadi*, and *nanti*.

Adverbs of time in the form of nominal phrases can be as repetition of words, such as *pagipagi*, *malam-malam*, *siang-siang*, and *sore-sore*. They can also be combined such as *sementara lagi*, *kemarin dulu*, dan *tidak lama kemudian*.

- 1) Saatnya telah tiba untuk pergi *sekarang*.
Aslyores aniok mayaam tarepek
It's time to go now.
- 2) Dia biasanya datang ke kantor pagi-pagi.
Kabiasaan na maay angkentor mamondo
He usually comes to the office in the morning.
- 3) Ada apa kamu datang malam-malam begini?
A weyan sapa kemo maay wersi kaniok
Why did you come this night?
- 4) Dia mengerjakan tugas itu sampai pukul lima.
Sia tumawoi in tatowayen tu aker jam 5
He did his task until at five o'clock.
- 5) Pemerintah mengumumkan kenaikan bensin *kemarin*.
Se pemerintah melaket harga in solo kawii.
The government announced the fuel rates enhancement yesterday.

- 6) *Tadi dia menanyakan lagi soal itu.*
Tarepek sia mamoy si tawoyen tu.
He asked about that again.
- 7) *Saya akan menemanimu sampai hari Minggu.*
Yaky kumora pico akan ina nari duminggu.
I will accompany you until Sunday.
- 8) *Ibu saya akan membeli baju baru untuk kami minggu depan.*
Si mamaku tu tumeles karai weru weey a cami.
My mom will buy new clothes for us next week.

Based on the data for the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian and the Tontemboan Regional languages have the same adverbs of time in the form of single words, but the repetition forms of time adverbs in Indonesian do not occur in the Tontemboan languages.

3.3 Adverbs of Tool

Adverb of tool is a description that explains about the existence of a tool used to perform an action. The definition of a tool in this case does not have to be a concrete object. Prepositional phrases that state the adverb of tool can appear with or without prepositions. Example:

- 1) *Kami biasanya pergi ke kebun dengan motor.*
Biasa ami mayak anuma kerepi in motor
We usually go to the office by motorcycle.

Adverbs of tools are marked with or without the prepositions, even though these prepositions are also used to mark accompanying adverbs and adverbs of manner. Therefore, it is not impossible that there are parallel forms as in the following three examples.

- 2) *Saya bekerja dengan orang besar.*
Yaku tu mawoy kerepi etow wangker
I work with big people.
- 3) *Saya bekerja dengan kemauan besar.*
Yaku tumawoy ma ulit ulit
I work will big motivation.
- 4) *Saya bekerja dengan kapak besar.*
Yaku tumawoy im pati wangker
I work with big axes.

The outer form of sentence no. 2), 3) and 4) above is similar. However, if we pay more attention, the types of nouns that stand in the right of the preposition, will be shown that 2) *orang* are living things so that with *orang besar* they must state accompanying description. On the other hand, *dengan kehendak besar* in sentence 3) and *dengan kapak besar* in sentence 4) cannot be paired with adverbs because neither the noun nor the ax are not living things. Based on the semantic characteristics found in the noun *kemauan* and *kapak*, phrases *dengan kemauan besar* are considered adverbs of method, whereas *dengan kapak besar* are adverbs of tools. This distinctions are reinforced by the fact that the three sentences answer different questions. For example:

- 5) a. *Bagaimana dia bekerja?*
Tambisa sia tumawoy
How did she work?
b. *Dia bekerja dengan kemauan besar.*
Sia tumawoy kerapi kasaleana im nesa
She work will big motivation.
- 6) a. *Dengan siapa dia bekerja?*
Karapi sey sia tumawoy
With whom was she work with?

- b. Dia bekerja *dengan orang besar*.
Sia tumawoy kerapi etow wangker
She worked with big person.
- 7) a. Dengan apa dia bekerja?
Kerapi sapa sia tumawoy
How does she work?
b. Dia bekerja *dengan kapak besar*.
Sia tumawoy kerepi im pati wangker.
She works with big axes.
- 8) Mereka membuka pintu itu *dengan kunci cadangan*.
Sera mukak im papalen kampi in kunci reserep.
They open the door with a spare key.
- 9) Dia tidak dapat membaca *tanpa kaca mata*
Sia cetoro maca seraca wane kaca mata
She cannot read without the glasses.
- 3.4 Adverbs of Purpose

Adverb of purpose states the direction, or intent of the action or event. The adverb of purpose is always in the form of a prepositional phrase and the prepositions used are *demi*, *bagi*, *guna*, dan *untuk*. The four prepositions are followed by a nominal phrase as in the following example.

- 1) Dia bersedia berkorban *demi* kepentingan negara.
Sia sumadia kumorban ingka pentingan i Negara
He is willing to scarify for the common interest.
- 2) Marilah kita mengheningkan cipta *bagi* para pahlawan.
Mayo kita kumuru se pahlawan
Let us have a moment of silent remembering out heroes.
- 3) Masih adakah orang yang rela berkorban *guna* kepentingan umum?
Aweyan neh setow kumorban ingkapentingan mbeys
Is there anyone who is willing to scarify for common interest?
- 4) Dia memang mempunyai tekad besar *untuk* merantau.
Sia memang nekat mange endoong etow
He has big motivation to go wander.
- 5) Saya sengaja tinggal di kota kecil *agar* dapat mengetahui kehidupan di sana.
Yaku sumarsaja mentok ang kuketaltekek
I live in a small city so that I know how it is to live there.
- 6) Kami pergi *biar* dia mengerjakan pekerjaannya.
Kami mange mande sia tumawoy intaweyena i nesa
We go so that he can do his work.
- 7) Pak Eden membanting tulang *demi* menafkahi anak dan istrinya.
Si pa Eden tumawoy mati-matian mongkes simporenu kerapi setoyaas
Pak Eden works hard for his daughter and wife.
- 8) Dia berdoa *untuk* kesembuhan ibunya.
Sunonbeyas sia an kalooren i manuana
He prayed for his mother health.

Based on the data for the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian language and the

Tontemboan languages have the same description of purpose, but some words in Indonesian language cannot be used in the Tontemboan languages.

3.5 ADVERBS OF MANNER

Adverb of manner describes about how an event takes place. Like adverbs of time, adverbs of manner can be either a single word or a prepositional phrase. The singular word usually comes with the form of adjective enclosed with *se...-nya*. In the following examples, adverb of manner is expressed through the words *secepatnya*, *dan sepenuhnya*.

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- 1) Dia berbicara *seenaknya* dengan atasannya.
Sia mapaar kerapi siyatesannya
She talked with his casually to her superiors.
 - 2) Masalah itu harus diselesaikan *secepatnya*.
Si perkara itu pariorioeren
The problem should be cleared soon.
 - 3) Kami percayakan soal ini *sepenuhnya* kepada Anda.
Si soal aniok sarekan ami a sia
The fully trusted this to you.

Prepositional phrases that express adverbs of manner consist of prepositions *dengan*, *secara*, or *tanpa* followed by adjective phrases or nominal phrases as complements. Prepositions can usually only be followed by a nominal phrase as a complement. If the preposition's complement is a repetitive adjective, the preposition that precedes it can be omitted (see 4b) and 5b)). Meanwhile, if the adverb comes only in a prepositional phrase with an adjective, not in a repetitive form, the preposition cannot be omitted (see 6b) and 7b).

- 4) a. Kereta itu pun meninggalkan stasiun *dengan* perlahan-lahan.
Si kereta tu mekau i stasiun mongegerger.
The train leaves the station slowly.
b. Kereta itu pun meninggalkan stasiun perlahan-lahan.
Si kereta ta melekan i stasiun imarseger geger
The train leaves the station slowly.
- 5) a. Beri tahu kepada adikmu *secara* baik-baik.
Cua asi tuaninn kerepi maloon looren
Tell it to your sister nicely.
b. Beri tahu kepada adikmu baik-baik.
Cua asi tuworinn maloon lороon.
Tell it to your sister nicely.
- 6) a. Dia menjawab pertanyaan itu *dengan* tegas.
Sia jumaweb si pertanyaan tu kerepi in tegas
She answered the questions assertively.
b. *Dia menjawab pertanyaan itu tegas.
Sia jumaweb si pertanyaan tu kerepi in tegas
She answered the questions assertively
- 7) a. Dia menerangkan soal itu *dengan* jelas.
Sia kemeranken si soal tu kerapi ulit
She explains the questions assertively.
b. *Dia menerangkan soal itu jelas.
Sia kemeranken si soal tu kerapi ulit.
She explains the questions assertively.

If the preposition's complement comes as a nominal phrase, the preposition can come with the words *dengan*, *secara*, *atau* *tanpa*. Prepositions can generally be replaced by *cara*.

Examples (8)—(10) are acceptable, but (11b) are not acceptable.

- 8) a. Marilah kita selesaikan masalah ini *secara* baik.
Mayo kita sumelesalken si masalah anyok kerapi meleorooran
Let us clear this problem in good a way.
b. Marilah kita selesaikan masalah ini dengan cara baik.
Mayo kita sumelesalken si masalah anyok kerapi meleoora
Let us clear this problem in good way.
- 9) *Tanpa* kemauan besar tidak akan berhasil.
Aca kerapi indieket ico aca mamuali
Without big willingness, it won't work.

- 10)a. Kita lebih baik menyelesaikan masalah ini *secara* kekeluargaan.
Kita sumelasalkan masalah anyok anuntep imporeleta
Let us clear this problem in a good way.
- b. Kita lebih baik menyelesaikan masalah ini dengan cara kekeluargaan.
Kita sumelasalkan masalah anyok anuntep imporeleta
It is better for us to clear this problem in a good way.
- 11)Dia bekerja *dengan* kemauan besar.
Sia tumewoi andeken kerapi maulit ulit
He works with big motivations,

Adverbs of manner can also be formed by adding the form *se-...-nya* to certain repetitive words.

Example:

- 12) Kamu boleh makan *sepuas-puasnya*. → sepuasnya
Kamo kuman akan i mawesuk
You can eat as much as you can
- 13) Carilah contoh *sebanyak-banyaknya*. ---→sebanyaknya
Pangere nange maka keli-keli
You can eat as much as possible.
- (14) Kita harus menyelesaikan masalah ini *secepat-cepatnya*. --→secepatnya
Kita mapora pora sumelelaikansi masalah aniok
We must clear this problem as soon as possible.

Another form of adverb is the repetition of certain words followed by an affix. Sometimes it can also be preceded by a preposition. Example:

- 15) Waktu itu kami berjuang *mati-matian*.
Si waktu tu kami ma berjuang mati matian
We fight so hard that time.
- 16) Dia *terang-terangan* menolak ajakan siapa pun untuk berbuat curang.
Sia kumeleng memak in kamesean
He frankly rejected to ask anyone to cheat.

Adverbs of manner can also be in the form of a *se-* followed by a certain word. The word *demi* is often used as a combination. Example:

- 17) a. Mereka mundur *selangkah*.
Sera mundur esa langka
They take one step back.
- b. *Selangkah demi selangkah* kami pun bergerak terus.
 We keep moving step by step.
Esa langka kami mecok lema laas
- 18) Kemajuan tetap ada meskipun *sedikit demi sedikit*.
Si toyang tu tumuruk in kepeadeknya made pire kek
There is a progress goes even it comes slowly.
- 19) a. Silakan maju *setapak*.
Mayak mange esa langka
One step forward.
- b. Dari posisi paling belakang akhirnya pebalap itu merangkak *setahap demi setahap* maju ke posisi depan.
Ampaling somoi sia lumangkey se kerepi na andior
The racer comes forward from the back to front.

3.6 ADVERBS OF ACCOMPANIMENT

Adverb of accompaniment is an adverb that states whether there are other people accompanying in carrying out an action. The accompanying statement is expressed by combining prepositions *dengan*, *tanpa*, *atau bersama* with living things nominal phrases form.

Example:

- 1) Ibu pergi ke Manado *dengan saya*.
Si mamaku mange am benang kerepiku
My mom went to Manado with me.
- 2) Dia meramaikan acara itu *dengan rekan-rekannya*.
Sia rumame si acara tu kerepi na
He enlivened the party with his friends.
- 3) Pak Niko berangkat ke Israel *tanpa istrinya*.
Papa niko mange ang Israel aca kerepi penenoanya
Mr. Niko went to Israel without his wife.
- 4) Pemerintah bekerja *bersama rakyat*.
Se pemerintah tumawoy mewali wali kerepi e rakyat
The government works along with the people.

Based on the data from the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian and the Tontemboan language have similar accompanying statements, but the prepositions *dengan*, *tanpa*, *dan bersama* in Indonesian can only with paired with the word *kerepi* in the Tontemboan language.

3.7 COMPARATIVE ADVERBS

Comparative Adverb (or similarity) describes about equality, similarity, or difference between a situation, event, or action and another situation, event, or action. The form of the adverb is always in the form of a phrase with a preposition, such as *laksana*, *sebagai*, *atau seperti*.

Example:

- 1) Berpikirlah *seperti orang dewasa*
Mikir mange tanu semama tua
Think like an adult.
- 2) Apakah selamanya mereka akan hidup *sebagai* buruh harian?
Sapakeh sera tu mawoi susun i nendo
Will they live forever as a labourer?

Based on the data for the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian language and the Tontemboan language have the same comparative adverbs.

3.8 ADVERBS OF INTERCHANGEABILITY

Adverb of Interchangeability states about an action that occurs reciprocally. Adverbs of Interchangeability are stated with *satu sama lain* or *saling* before the verb or at the end of the sentence.

- 1) a. Kedua desa itu bersepakat untuk tidak *menyerang satu sama lain*.
Serua roong itu meromaang aca toro masekesekean
Those two villages make a deal that they won't attack each other.
- b. Kedua desa itu bersepakat untuk *tidak saling menyerang*.
Serua roong tu meromaang aca toro masekesekean

Those two villages make a deal that they won't attack each other.

- 2) a. Indonesia dan Australia berjanji akan menghormati satu sama lain.
Indonesia Australia meromaan aca toro meysesean
Indonesia and Australia promises to respect each other.
- b. Indonesia dan Australia berjanji akan saling menghormati.
Indonesi Australia ose meromemetaen seleng memberdekan
Indonesia and Australia respect each other.

Based on the data for the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian and the Tontemboan Regional languages have the same Adverbs of interchangeability.

3.9 ADVERBS OF CAUSATIVE

Adverb of causative states about the cause or reason for the occurrence of a condition, event, or action. The form of the statement is always in the form of a construction that begins with the words *karena*, *lantaran*, *sebab*, *berkat*, *gara-gara*, or *mentang-mentang*.

- 1) Banyak pemimpin dunia jatuh *karena* korupsi
Kekelian se pemimpin ase kayobaa nanyo papan
There are so many leaders fall down because of corruptions.
- 2) Banyak orang merantau *lantaran* ingin memperbaiki kehidupannya.
Keliton surerskot papaan muteri in ketowana
Many people come wander to fix their live.
- 3) Stella datang terlambat *sebab* anaknya sakit.
Si stela maay sosomoy larten sitoyaan sumeket
Stella came late because her daughter is sick.
- 4) *Berkat* ketekunannya, Stella berhasil meraih cita-citanya.
Komang lekekna sia makere pa wawona
Because of her persistent, Stella achieved her goals.
- 5) *Gara-gara* tingkah laku anaknya, kedua orang tua itu dijauhi para tetangganya.
Lantara serua toyaang tu tinayangaren e ketetangga
Because of their children's attitude, the parents are avoided by the neighbor.
- 6) Mereka berbuat seenaknya *mentang-mentang* kaya.
Sera memek mange kasakan nerakanton tousia
They do whatever they want just because they're rich.

Gara-gara and *mentang-mentang* are not included in Indonesian standard spoken language, these words generally denote about negative causes, while *berkat* usually denotes about positive causes.

3.10 ADVERBS OF CONSEQUENCE

Adverb of Consequences describes about the cause or consequences of a situation, event, or action. This adverb always comes in the form of a construction with a conjunction such as *akibat*, *sehingga*, atau *sampai-sampai*.

- 1) Hutan itu gundul *akibat* pembalakan liar.
Si taluntu ayowane sapa sapa kertau setou
That wood is bared because of the wild buning.
- 2) Dia bekerja tidak kenal waktu *sehingga* lupa makan.
Sia tumawoy aca osia lupa kuman
He worked over-timed until he forgot to eat.
- 3) Ia terlalu sibuk *sampai-sampai* pulang larut malam.
Lantaran kasibukana osia mareng katoora imbengi
He is too busy until he went home late at night.

Based on the data for the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian language and the Tontemboan language have the same adverbs of consequence.

3.11 ADVERBS OF QUANTITY

Adverb of quantity states about the amount of something that are being discussed. Adverbs of quantity are indicated by words, *sebanyak, sedikit, atau sama sekali*.

- 1) Ayah saya mempunyai sapi *sebanyak* sepuluh ekor.
Si papaku make punya sapi sangapuluh ekor
My father has fifty cows.
- 2) Ia menambahkan gula *sedikit* ke dalam kopi itu.
Sia mewes minok oula pira anuntep in kopi.
She puts the sugar little by little to the coffee.

Based on the data for the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian language and the Tontemboan language have the same adverb of quantity, but there are things that cannot be identified in the Tontemboan language, such as number 1) the word *sebanyak* is not appear in Tontemboan language sentence form.

3.12 ADVERBS OF QUALITY

Adverb of Quality elucidates the level of something being discussed. Quality information is marked with *agak, amat, paling, sangat, atau terlalu*.

- 1) Mereka berbicara *agak* keras.
Sera meromaan talusem ketek
They talk a little loudly.
- 2) Pak Ferry mengendarai mobil itu *amat* pelan.
Si bapak ferry mantar in oto pelung ngenger
Mr. Ferry drives the car really slowly.
- 3) Mereka hadir dalam pertemuan itu *paling* awal.
Sera lumili mange paling merior rior
They attend the meeting early.
- 4) Jawabannya *sangat* meyakinkan.
Sesowetna paling ulit ulit
The answer is really trusted.
- 5) Kadang-kadang kita menanggapi suatu masalah *terlalu* berlebihan.
Maka keli keli kita tumangkek malebebean
Sometimes we take a problem too seriously.

Based on the data for the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian language and Tontemboan language have the same Adverb of quality.

3.13 ADVERBS OF VIEWPOINT

Adverb of Viewpoint explicates about a reference that is relevant to the truth of what is stated in that clause. Adverb of viewpoint usually comes with the forms of *seperti dari sudut, menurut...., dilihat dari, dan secara*

- 1) *Dari sudut* ilmu pengetahuan, yang ia katakan benar.
Andoro ing kepandeyang acuama butul
From the knowledge perspective, what he is saying is true.
- 2) *Menurut* dokter, Tasya harus istirahat.
Acuai dokter si tasya musti istirahat
According to the doctor, Tasya must take a rest.

Based on the data for the two languages above, it appears that both Indonesian language and Tontemboan language have the same Adverb of quality.

In addition to these thirteen types of adverbs, there are also other types of adverbs that appear with the form of subordinate clauses, namely conditional adverb, presuppositional adverb, concessional adverb, and outcome adverbs. Shown in the following description.

3.14 ADVERBS OF REQUIREMENT

Adverb of requirement is found in the sentences where the subordinate clause states the requirement for the implementation of what is referred to in the main clause, the conjunctions that are commonly used are *jika(lau)*, *kalau*, dan *asal (kan)*. Besides, the conjunction *kalau*, *(apa)bila*, and *bilamana* are usually used in the sentences those words indicate time.

- 1) *Jika* Anda mau mendengarkannya, saya tentu senang sekali menceritakannya.
Sake masalek lumnga paling senang linsoaken
If you want to listen to it, I would happily tell it.
- 2) Anda boleh makan makanan yang mengandung lemak *asalkan* mengetahui batas jumlah lemak yang tidak akan mengganggu kesehatan Anda.
ketona kuman se keru kenel asal keles nu embetes
You can eat food that contains fat if
- 3) Hatiku bertambah senang *apabila* aku teringat bahwa akulah yang tertua.
Nakwa paling senang saya meleteng yaku pola matua
My heart go happy if I remember that I am the oldest.

Conjunctions that refer the Adverbs indicate that the relationship in sentence number 3 above is unclear.

3.15 CONDITIONAL ADVERBS

Adverb of Conditional states about the conditional relations in complex sentences in which the subordinate clause states about the supposition that might occur after the realization of the main clause. The most commonly used conjunction is *seandainya*. If the supposition is related to 'uncertainty', the conjunctions used are *kalau-kalau* or *barangkali*.

- 1) *Seandainya* para anggota kelompok menerima aturan itu, selesailah seluruh permasalahan tersebut.
Sakelelen kelompok tu masalah makepan pakua masaalek
If the other member accept that rules, the problems will be over.
- 2) Sudah dua hari ia tidak masuk *jangan-jangan* ia sakit.
Rua mengondo sia ace muntep yore sia semekit
She didn't come to work for two days, maybe she's sick.
- 3) Ia menengok keluar *kalau-kalau* anaknya sudah datang
Sumere ang kesot sia sa toyangan mereyen
She looks outside to see if her daughter comes
- 4) Ia menengok ke luar *barangkali* anaknya sudah datang.
Sia sumere ang kesot papa manengan
She looks outside to see if maybe her daughter comes

It can be seen from the example sentence above, sentence number 4) has no conjunction. The conjunctions *seandainya*, *jangan-jangan*, dan *sa* are also exist in the Tontemboan language.

3.16 CONSENSUAL ADVERBS

Concessive adverbs are found in complex sentences whose subordinate clauses contain statements that contradict the meaning of the main clause, but do not change the reality in the main clause. The conjunction used are *walaupun*, *meskipun*, *sekalipun*, *biarpun*, *kendatipun*, *sekalipun*, and *betapapun*. The variety of standard conjunctions *walaupun/meskipun* are not followed by the word *tetapi*.

Consensual Adverb can also be marked with the particle *pun* in the subordinate clause because the particle can be replaced with *walaupun* or *meskipun* so that *mahal pun* can be replaced with *walaupun mahal* or *meskipun mahal*.

- 1) *Walaupun* hatinya sangat sedih, dia tidak pernah menangis di hadapanku.
Made sumakit enatena alakewisa sia maerek an dior ku
Although his heart were sad, he never cried in front of me.
- 2) Dia akan pergi *sekalipun* kami coba menahannya.
Sia pasti manede tahas ngenami
He will still go even though we try to hold him.
- 3) *Betapapun* sulitnya medan itu, kita harus melewatinya.
Mande si lele tu kelewoan tetep weyaangmi
No matter how hard the road, we must pass it by.
- 4) *Mahal pun*, buku itu dia beli juga.
Sosor si buku itu tetep telesana
Although the book was expensive, he bought it anyways.
- 5) *Walaupun mahal*, buku itu dia beli juga.
Made mahal telesana sibuku tu
Although the book was expensive, he bought it anyways.
- 6) *Meskipun mahal* buku itu dia beli juga.
Made sosor an harga I buku tu tetep telesana
Although the book was expensive, he bought it anyways.

Conjunctions that express the condescending relations are found in the six examples of Tontemboan language sentences above.

3.17 ADVERBS OF RESULT

Adverb of result applies to complex sentences whose subordinate clauses state the results or consequences of what is stated in the main clause. This relationship is usually expressed by using conjunctions, such as: *sehingga*, *sampai-sampai* and *maka*.

- 1) Pertemuan pemimpin kedua desa itu makin baik *sehingga* hubungan antarwarga desanya pun makin harmonis.
Petaepan etua tong tu pesungkukan tua toing tu melolo oranem
The meeting of the two village leaders run well, because of the relationship between the
Two villages are good.
- 2) Biaya pengobatannya sungguh mahal *sampai-sampai* semua perhiasan istrinya habis terjual.
Ongkos mange mubat sosor keli pakasa em barang mas aywangkernag
The treatment cost is really expensive until she has to sell all of his wife jewelries.
- 3) Kami tidak setuju, *maka* kami pun protes.
Aca setuju name aneitu protesen ami
We did not agree, because of that we complain.

There are no conjunctions that express the adverb of result in the three examples of Tontemboan language sentences above.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the descriptions in the results and discussion section above, it is concluded that the types of adverbs that fill syntactic functions in Indonesian and Tontemboan languages have similarities and differences. The similarities can be seen from the total number types of adverbs, there are thirteen types of adverbs as stated in the third edition of the the book *Tata Bahasa Baku Bahasa Indonesia*. The difference is that some adverb elements sentences in Indonesian language that used the prepositions and conjunctions cannot be identified in the Tontemboan local language.

Suggestions that can be put forward related to this research is the need to conduct another studies that can be put as articles by other researchers related to the syntactic function of object and complement in sentences with a contrastive approach.

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